

MAKE A GIFT

RNA22 v2 results

Results have been computed and are shown below. If there are no results shown, it means your chosen parameters yielded no results.

Note: The p-value represents the likelihood that the target site loci is random. That is, a lower p-value represents a greater chance that the loci contains a valid MRE

miR Name ▲	transcript name	leftmost position of predicted target site	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol)	heteroduplex	p value
hsa_mir_10b_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	15888	-16.20	TACAATGCTAGTTAAACAGGGTG : GTGTTTAAGCCAAGATGCCCAT	7.65E-2
hsa_mir_10b_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	19660	-14.70	CACCTTGATGG-ACAACAGGGTG : GTGTTTAAGCCAAGATGCCCAT	1.47E-1
hsa_mir_155_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	5282	-12.50	AACGTGTATCTGCCACTGCATTGT : TTGGGGATAGTGC-TAATCGTAATT	1.62E-1
hsa_mir_17_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	13978	-12.70	GAACGTGTAC--GCCAAGCTTTG : GATGGACGTGACATTCGTGAAAC	1.06E-1
hsa_mir_17_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	15536	-13.20	CTGTCACGGCCAATGTTAATGCACITTT GATGG--ACG-TGACA--TTCGTGAAAC	2.39E-1
hsa_mir_18a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	5565	-15.00	CTGTTATGTACATGGGCACACTTTC : GATAG-ACGTG-ATCTACGTGGAAT	2.28E-1
hsa_mir_18a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	15000	-14.30	TTATGAGGATCAAGATGCACITTT : GATAGCGTG-ATCTACGTGGAAT	1.34E-1
hsa_mir_18a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	15536	-13.70	CTGTCACGGCCAATGTTAATGCACITTT GATAG--ACG--TG-ATCTACGTGGAAT	2.39E-1
hsa_mir_18a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	16708	-14.70	CTGCTGACA-GAGAATTACATCTTT : GATAGAC-GTGATCT--ACGTGGAAT	2.73E-1
hsa_mir_18a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	22044	-14.10	CTA-GTGCGAATAATTGCACITTT GATAGCGT-GATCTACGTGGAAT	1.64E-1
hsa_mir_18a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	22330	-13.20	AGGTTGGACAGCTGGTCTGCAGCTTA : : : : GATAGAC--GTGATC--TACGTGGAAT	6.11E-2
hsa_mir_18a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	22978	-14.80	CTATCAGCCGGTAG-CACACCTTG GATAG-ACG-TGATCTACGTGGAAT	2.5E-1
hsa_mir_19a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	1715	-14.80	ACAAGTGCTTTTGTG-GAAACT : : ACATCACGTTGATACGTTTTGA	5.84E-2

miR Name ▲	transcript name ◆	leftmost position of predicted target site ◆	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol) ◆	heteroduplex	p value
hsa_mir_19a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	6451	-13.80	TG-AGTGTA-TGTG-AAAAC : : ACATCACGTTGATACGTTTGA	1.54E-1
hsa_mir_19a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	8789	-14.70	GGTGGTAGTTATACTAATGACAAAGCT : : : ACATCA-CG--TTGAT-AC-GTTTGA	2.78E-1
hsa_mir_19a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	10156	-13.40	CGTAGT-TTACTGTCCAAGACA : : ACATCACGTTGATACGTTTGA	2.65E-1
hsa_mir_19a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	13437	-12.10	TTCAGT-CAGCTGATGCACAATC : : : ACATCACGTTGAT-ACGTTTGA	1.89E-1
hsa_mir_19a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	26359	-13.90	TTGTGTGGTACTGCTCAATATT : : : ACATCACGT-TGAT-ACGTTTGA	3.9E-1
hsa_mir_19b_1_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	3582	-15.10	GC-GGACACAATCTGTAAACA : CGACCTACGTTGGACGTTTGA	1.52E-1
hsa_mir_19b_1_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	19595	-12.30	TCTGGA-ACACTTTTACAAGACT : : CGACCTACGTTGGACGTTTGA	3.25E-1
hsa_mir_19b_1_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	26358	-12.00	ATTGTGTGGTACTGCTCAATATT : : : CGACCTACGTTG--GACGTTTGA	3.9E-1
hsa_mir_19b_1_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	29172	-13.70	ATTGGCCGCAAT-TGCACAATT : : : CGACCTACGTTGGACGTTTGA	6.2E-2
hsa_mir_20a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	14358	-16.60	CATTCTGCATTGTGCAACTTTA : : : GATGGACGTGATTCGTGAAAT	2.42E-1
hsa_mir_20a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	27550	-13.70	AAATTTGACTG-ACTTGTCTTA : : : GATGGACGTGATTCGTGAAAT	3.76E-1
hsa_mir_210_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	28784	-16.90	TTCTACGCAGAAGGAGCAGAGGCG GTCACAGCC--ACC-CGTCCCGA	6.4E-3
hsa_mir_221_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	16379	-14.20	ATGTTTGCAATG--CTCCAGGT : : : TTTAGATGAACATACGGTCCA	2.39E-1
hsa_mir_221_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	28146	-15.40	CCTTTTACAATTAATGCCAGGA : TTTAGATG-TAACATACGGTCCA	2.39E-1
hsa_mir_222_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	4060	-12.80	AGATTCTGCCACTCTGTTAGTGAC : : TCCTAGATG-TGA--CCGATGACTC	3.66E-3
hsa_mir_222_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	7046	-18.40	TCTTACTGTACTGGTTACAGAG : : : TCCTAGATGTGACCGATGACTC	2.9E-1
hsa_mir_222_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	9927	-16.40	TGGAT-ACAACTAGCTACAGAG TCCTAGATGTGACCGATGACTC	2.32E-1
hsa_mir_222_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	21029	-14.60	GGGATCT-CATT-ATTAGTGAT : : :	7.09E-2

miR Name ▲	transcript name	leftmost position of predicted target site	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol)	heteroduplex	p value
				TCCTAGATGTGACCGATGACTC	
hsa_mir_31_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	1678	-13.40	AGAGATGCCATTATTTGGCA : : TCGATA - CGTCGTAGAACGGA	3.62E-1
hsa_mir_31_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	3581	-13.30	AGC - -GGACACAATCTTGCTA : TCGATACGGTCGTAGAACGGA	1.52E-1
hsa_mir_31_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	9483	-12.80	AATACAGTCATGTA - GTTGCTT : TCGATACGGT - CGTAGAACGGA	2.32E-1
hsa_mir_31_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	11178	-12.80	TGTTTTTGTACCTCTCTTGCCA : :: TCGA - TACGGTCG - -TAGAACGGA	3.43E-1
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	1183	-12.00	TGCGTCACCAAATGAATGCAACCA : : TCGTA - ACGT TGGCTAGGGTTGGA	9.19E-2
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	3024	-12.00	TGTATTGT - TCT - -TCTACCT : : : : TCGTAACGTTGGCTAGGGTTGGA	8.61E-3
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	6002	-13.80	GATCTTGTA - CC - AAACCAACCA : TCGTAACGTTGGCTAGGGTTGGA	1.29E-2
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	7085	-13.30	ACTAATGTCACT - ATTGCAACCT : : : TCGTAACGTTGGCTAGGGTTGGA	2.9E-1
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	12066	-12.50	TGC - TGGACACAGG - -GCAACCT : TCGTAAC - GT TGGCTAGGGTTGGA	9.78E-2
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	19933	-12.40	ACTGACATAGCCAAGAACCAACTG : : : TCGTAACGTTGG - -CTAGGGTTGGA	1.59E-1
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	21892	-13.22	AGATTCGAAGACCAGTCCCTACTT : : : TC - GTAACTGTGG - CTAGGGTTGGA	1.54E-1
hsa_mir_92a_1_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	26898	-13.20	GGCA - CTATTCTGA - CCAGACCG : : : TCGTAACGTTGGCTAGGGTTGGA	2.11E-1
hsa_mir_9_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	3868	-13.40	AAAGATCGCTGAGATTCTAAAGA : AGTATGTCGA - TCTATTGGTTTCT	2.08E-1
hsa_mir_9_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	9928	-12.30	GGATACAACCTAG - -CTACAGAGA : AGTATGTCGATCTATTGGTTTCT	2.32E-1
mir_21_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	5907	-14.20	CTTATAAATTGGATGGTGTG : TGTCGGGTAGCTGACCACAAC	2.98E-1
mir_21_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	9234	-15.10	AAAGATCAGAAGCTGGTGTGTT : TGTCGGGTAGCTGACCACAAC	3.03E-1
mir_21_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	14478	-14.60	CCACTTCAGAGACTAGGTGTG : TGTCGGGTAGCT - GA - CCACAAC	1.22E-1

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mir_21_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	22329	-14.00	CAGGTTGGACAGCTGGTGCTG : :: : : TGTCGGGTAGCTGACCACAAC	6.11E-2
mir_21_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	23053	-17.30	CCAACCA -CTAATGGTGTG TGTCGGGTAGCTGACCACAAC	5.13E-2

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